

EFFECT OF LIGHT PERIOD ON SPORE GERMINATION OF *NOTOTHYLAS KHASIANA* UDAR ET SINGH IN HALF KNOP'S LIQUID MEDIUM

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ABSTRACT

Present paper deals with the influence of light period on percentage of spore germination of *Notothylas khasiana* Udard et Singh. It was observed that short exposure to light (i.e. up to 4 hrs.) was ineffective in inducing the spore germination and spores of *Notothylas khasiana* require at least 5 hrs. daily photoperiod exposure to light.

Key words: *Notothylas khasiana*, spore germination, light

INTRODUCTION

Bryophytes have been considered of great fundamental importance in experimental botany. They contribute to our knowledge on various branches of plant sciences including genetics, experimental morphology, physiology and regeneration.

Spore is a specialized unicellular structure having potentiality of developing into a new individual. Spore germination is responsible for the spread of a species year after year. Various factors influence the process of spore germination and development of young gametophyte. However, main objective of the present investigation was to study the influence of light period on spore germination of *Notothylas khasiana* Udard et Singh.

Borodin (1868) while working on *Polytrichum commune*, noticed that in dark spores did not germinate. According to Heald (1898) Spores of bryophytes do not germinate in dark because of

failure of certain chemical processes necessary for germination to become active. In his review Meyer (1948) stated that in *Funaria hygrometrica*, some workers observed spore germination in light, whereas others reported spore germination both in dark and light.

Singh (1981) studied the influence of photoperiod on spore germination of *Targionia hypophylla*. It was observed that a minimum daily exposure for four hours to diffused day light was necessary for spore germination. Further, percentage of spore germination increase with increase in the daily illumination period up to 10 hours.

It was observed by Patidar and Kaul (1983) that a light duration of 10 hrs. and 5,000 lux light were optimum for vegetative growth in *Riccia gangetica*. Kessler (1914), Servettaz (1913) and von Ubisch (1913) reported spore germination in darkness. Vyas (1984) noticed that minimum exposure of 4 hours duration is essential for spore germination in natural diffused light.

Hughes (1962) reported the influence of day length on the development of the sporophyte of *Polytrichum aloides*.

Valanne (1966) noticed those very short periods of day length exposure to be ineffective in spore germination of *Ceratodon purpureus* and *Funaria hygrometrica*. A mean period of six hours exposure to white light is necessary before germination could take place.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Living materials of *Notothylas khasiana* was collected from Pavagadh, Gujarat. Capsules of *Notothylas khasiana* Udar et Singh were surface sterilized with 2% of calcium hypochlorite solution. To prepare spore suspension in double distilled water, sterilized capsules were ruptured

to liberate the spores. 0.01ml of well shaken spore suspension which contains approximately 30 spores was spread on whatman's filter paper no. 1 in the petri dish.

To observe the effect of different light period petri dishes were kept under dark and different day length conditions (i.e. 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9 & 10 hours) in a growth chamber with flourscent tube light with an intensity of 3500 to 4500 lux and temperature was maintained at $25 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$. Observations were recorded at 10th, 20th and 30th day. Each experiment was comprised a minimum of three replicates and repeated thrice.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

C Spore germination did not take place in dark and even up to 4 hrs daily photo period

Table-1: Showing effect of light period on spore germination of *Notothylas khasiana* Udar et Singh in Half Knop's liquid medium.

Light period (in hrs.)	10 th day	20 th day	30 th day
Dark	-	-	-
1	-	-	-
2	-	-	-
3	-	-	-
4	-	-	-
5	28.89	41.11	46.67
6	38.89	52.22	60.00
7	45.56	56.67	64.44
8	51.11	64.44	71.11
9	60.00	68.89	74.44
10	63.33	73.33	80.00

CRD ANOVA for 10th day

SN.	SOURCE	DF	MS	F	SE	CD(5%)	CD(1%)
1	Treatment	5	505.80205	51.210**	1.81	5.591	7.841

CRD ANOVA For 20th day

SN.	SOURCE	DF	MS	F	SE	CD(5%)	CD(1%)
1	Treatment	5	421.83927	27.335**	2.27	6.989	9.801

CRD ANOVA for 30th day

SN.	SOURCE	DF	MS	F	SE	CD(5%)	CD(1%)
1	Treatment	5	423.33178	16.329**	2.94	9.058	12.704

** = Significant at 1% level of significance

exposure. Spores of *Notothylas khasiana* require at least 5 hours daily exposure to light. An increase in germination percentage was noticed with increase in light duration and under 10 hours daily photoperiod exposure maximum percentage of germination was observed.

On 10th day percentage of spore germination were 28.89, 38.89, 45.56, 51.11, 60.00 and 63.33 on giving daily photo period exposure of 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 hrs respectively (Figure-1).

A positive relationship was noticed between time period and spore germination percentage i.e. percentage of spore germination were higher at 20th and 30th day as compared to 10th day even on giving the same photo period exposure (as shown in table-1).

It is revealed from the statistical analysis that difference between treatments was significant at all the time period.

Figure-1. Effect of light period on spore germination of *Notothylas khasiana* Udar et Singh in Half Knop's liquid medium

The possible reason of failure of spore germination in dark and daily photoperiod exposure up to 4 hrs. may be failure of certain chemical processes necessary for germination to become active in dark. For the germination of spores minimum five hours daily photoperiod is essential

Results of the present work are in agreement with the results of Borodin (1868) in *Polytrichum commune*, Inoue (1960) in some

members of Marchantiales, Valanne (1966) in *Ceratodon purpureus* and *Funaria hygrometrica* who observed failure of spore germination in dark and not with Kessler (1914), Servettaz (1913) and von Ubisch (1913) who reported spore germination in darkness.

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